

the yield of six cultures — IR8, IR2797-105-2-2-3, IR4219-35-3, IR4427-315-2-3, BR51-91-6, and IR5105-93-2-2 — were not significantly lower in P₀ and P₁. BR51-91-6 performed best in both P₀ and P₁.

Other top yielders were IR34, IR2823-103-5-1A, and IR2823-103-5-1B, but yields between the two levels differed significantly. Panicle numbers were significantly lower in P₀ than in P₁ in IR20, IR2823-103-5-1A, and IR1514A-E666. Straw production was considerably lower in P₀ in four cultures:

IR2061-628-1-6-4-3, IR2823-103-5-1A, IR1514A-E666, and IR2797-105-2-2.

Varietal differences were found in P content of grain and straw. But P content was not related to varietal reaction to P deficiency.

Field observations showed that early growth was suppressed considerably in P₀ because of P deficiency, and that genotypes varied in degree of suppression. But the visible differences lessened after the maximum tillering stage and were minimum by flowering. Furthermore, flowering was delayed from 2 to 9 days

in many entries in P₀. The late-maturing cultures may recover better from initial depression (caused by P deficiency) than the early maturing ones.

Overall, IR34, BR51-91-6, and IR1505-93-2-2 could be regarded as tolerant. Six others, IR40, IR1514A-E666, IR2061-628-1-6-4-3, IR2823-103-5-1A, IR2797-105-2-2, and IR4707-123-3A could be considered sensitive.

The test is being repeated in the 1978 wet season. □

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Rice cold tolerance workshop in Korea

Scientists from six national programs and IRRI participated in a workshop on cold tolerance in rice in the Republic of Korea, 16-19 September 1978. The workshop was sponsored by the Korean Office of Rural Development (ORD) and the UNDP-funded International Rice Testing Program (IRTP), coordinated by IRRI. Before the workshop, some of the scientists participated in an IRTP cold tolerance monitoring tour in the Indian states of Kashmir and Himachal Pradesh, and in Nepal.

Rice in the temperate areas and in many high-elevation areas in the tropics suffers from cool temperature during the seeding stage or at flowering. Most rice farmers in the temperate regions grow japonica varieties, but tropical farmers prefer indicas. Indicas have higher yield potential but they are more susceptible to cool temperature. Cooperative efforts are needed to combine the cold tolerance of japonica varieties with the high yield potential of the indica varieties.

Korean scientists have crossed indica and japonica germplasm to develop high yielding rice varieties with japonica grain quality and some cold tolerance. They have developed techniques to systematically evaluate their breeding materials for cold tolerance and have

successfully integrated research with extension and farmers' training programs to implement research results quickly. Consequently, Korean rice production has increased dramatically since 1970.

In 1977 national rice yields were the highest in the world — average of 4.94 t/ha of milled rice. Thus, it was fitting that Korea host the first International Rice Cold Tolerance Workshop.

The objective of the workshop and the IRTP monitoring tour was to review the current status of breeding for cold tolerance and to evaluate entries in the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery (IRCTN). ORD Director General In Hwan Kim challenged the group to develop better varieties with cold tolerance, blast resistance, and acceptable grain quality. He said that although Korean production had increased substantially, the process of varietal improvement is continuous and never ending. Speakers from the various countries outlined their cold temperature problems and current research programs.

Participants made the following recommendations to improve collaboration work and speed the development of cold-tolerant varieties;

1. The rice growing environment of cool areas should be characterized.
2. Screening methodologies should be improved and expanded.

3. The rapid generation advance (RGA) method should be used to rapidly develop more diverse germplasm.

4. The IRCTN should be reorganized to maximize the utilization of nursery entries.

5. Young scientists from the cool regions should participate as a group in the GEU training program so they can become acquainted with new cold-tolerance screening methodology and share professional experiences. □

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